

The lateral area of sine functions

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We view a revolution solid around the x-axis:

The known formula of lateral area can be written:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \int_{x_1}^{x_2} f(x) \cdot \sqrt{1 + f'(x)^2} dx$$

We choose the function: $f(x) = a \cdot \sin(m \cdot x)$ $m > 0$

We assume $a > 0$, we get for the lateral area:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \int_{x_1}^{x_2} a \cdot \sin(mx) \cdot \sqrt{1 + a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2} dx$$

with the differentiation: $f'(x) = a \cdot m \cdot \cos(mx)$

We show the following formula of lateral area:

$$M = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \left[\frac{a m \cdot \cos(mx) \cdot \sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1} + a \operatorname{arcsinh}(a m \cos(mx))}{-2 m^2} \right]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

$$= 2 \cdot \pi \left[F(x) \right]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

Proof with differentiation of F(x):

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} \left(a m \cos(mx) \cdot \sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1} \right) \\ &= -a m^2 \sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1} \cdot \sin(mx) \\ & \quad - \frac{a^3 m^4 (\cos(mx))^2 \cdot \sin(mx)}{\sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \operatorname{arcsinh}(a m \cos(mx)) = \frac{-a m^2 \sin(mx)}{\sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1}}$$

We construct the value:

$$A = \sqrt{a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1}$$

$$\left[-2m^2 F(x) \right]'(x) = -am^2 \cdot A \cdot \sin(mx) -$$

$$- \frac{a^3 m^4 (\cos(mx))^2 \cdot \sin(mx)}{A} - \frac{am^2 \cdot \sin(mx)}{A}$$

$$= \frac{1}{A} \left[-am^2 A^2 \sin(mx) - a^3 m^4 (\cos(mx))^2 \cdot \sin(mx) - am^2 \sin(mx) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{A} \left[-am^2 (a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1) \cdot \sin(mx) - a^3 m^4 (\cos(mx))^2 \sin(mx) - am^2 \sin(mx) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{A} \left[-2a^3 m^4 (\cos(mx))^2 \cdot \sin(mx) - 2am^2 \sin(mx) \right]$$

$$= -\frac{m^2}{A} \cdot 2 \cdot a \cdot \sin(mx) \cdot \left[a^2 m^2 (\cos(mx))^2 + 1 \right]$$

$$= -2m^2 a \cdot \sin(mx) \cdot A$$

The differentiation is equal to the integrand. The proof is done.